

after incineration in a previously weighed platinum crucible, was ignited to ThO_2 at $600-700^\circ$, and the thorium content determined from the weight of ThO_2 left.

Results and Discussion

Thorium, alone and in presence of interfering metals, was determined several times using the new reagent. Encouraged by the excellent accuracy and precision of the results obtained (Table 1), further investigation was undertaken. It was found that even ten times excess of chloride, nitrate, sulphate and acetate are tolerated in these determinations. Comparative evaluation of the performance of the new reagent, with that of oxalic acid, revealed that the two methods are almost equally effective in determining thorium (Table 1). However, unlike the oxalic acid method in which the precipitate needs long settling time, the product obtained with the new reagent is ready for filtration minutes after its precipitation. The resulting rapidity of determination thus renders the new reagent preferable to oxalic acid, the most commonly used reagent for the purpose. Since the best analytical results for thorium are obtained gravimetrically¹, the expeditiousness of the new method holds considerable promise.

TABLE 1—GRAVIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF THORIUM*

Sl. no.	Weight of ThO_2 based on thorium content of sample used g	Weight of ThO_2 , g Using oxalic Acid (A)	Weight of ThO_2 , g Using KH Nap : gly (B)	Error, % (A)	Error, % (B)
1	0.0508	0.0510	0.0508	0.39	0.00
2	0.0636	0.0638	0.0638	0.31	0.31
3	0.0762	0.0766	0.0764	0.52	0.26
4	0.0478	0.0478	0.0476	0.00	0.42
5	0.0598	0.0596	0.0596	0.33	0.33
6	0.0718	0.0716	0.0718	0.28	0.00
7	—	0.0770	0.0768	—	—
8	—	0.0960	0.0962	—	—

$\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ used in Sl. nos. 1 to 3. A synthetic mixture, approximating monazite in composition, used in nos. 4 to 6, and a sample of Travancore monazite used in nos. 7 and 8. Interfering ions (Sl. nos. 4 to 8) eliminated by usual methods, before precipitating thorium.

Elemental analysis of the complex formed with the new reagent is in agreement with 1 : 2 thorium-ligand stoichiometry. The complex is a non-electrolyte, since it is non-conducting in DMF. Infrared spectral data revealed that the reagent is a dibasic tridentate ONO donor³, and that the complex is representable as $[\text{Th}(\text{Nap : gly})_2]\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Thermogravimetric analysis clearly indicated that a molecule of water is lost quantitatively from the complex in the temperature range $95-105^\circ$. Decomposition of the remainder of the complex is slow, but is complete at 600° leaving behind ThO_2 .

Composition of the complex precipitated in different experiments varied slightly, evidently because in the case of thorium^{1,2,5} coordination by

OH is not precluded fully even at pH 4. Hence, as in the other methods², direct weighing of the precipitate is not recommended.

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Trace Determination of Arsenic and Cobalt by Differential Pulse Polarography

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A precise, accurate and sensitive technique developed for trace determination of arsenic and cobalt gains importance as the former is a poison and also a potential carcinogen¹, while the latter is involved in numerous enzymatic reactions. References of their analysis by a wide variety of techniques, like atomic absorption spectroscopy^{2,3}, gas chromatography^{4,5}, polarography^{6,7} and inverse voltammetry^{8,9} are found in literature. A highly sensitive and particularly reliable analytical procedure for precise determination of arsenic and cobalt by differential pulse polarography is reported in the present communication.

Experimental

Cobaltous sulphate (A.R., S.M.) and sodium arsenite (Riedel) were used in the preparation of 0.1M stock solutions of Co^{II} and As^{III} in water. Triple-distilled water was used throughout the studies. 1% stock solutions of bromophenol blue (BPB) and Triton-X-100 were prepared in water and used after suitable dilutions to 0.01% working solutions. A 0.1% solution of gelatin was prepared afresh each day owing to its unstable nature. All other normal precautions of trace analysis were taken throughout the work.

Polarograms were recorded on a Metrom-E-506 Polarecord with E-505 series-03 polarography stand. A three-electrode system of DME as indicator electrode and two Ag/AgCl electrodes as

reference and auxiliary electrode was used. The recorder settings were as follows.

	Co ^{II}	As ^{III}
Scan range, V	-0.6 to -3.0	0.0 to -1.5
Scan rate, mV sec ⁻¹	24	20
Paper speed, mm min ⁻¹	120	200
Drop rate, sec	1.0	0.6
Pulse amplitude, mV	25	35
Temperature of measurement, °C	26	26

Concentrations both As^{III} and Co^{II} were maintained at 5 ppm throughout the studies for ascertaining best suitable determination conditions. The final volume was always made upto 50 ml with triple-distilled water. Nitrogen gas was passed through the solution prior to the determination so as to expel dissolved oxygen.

Results and Discussion

Cobalt undergoes reduction as $Co + 2e^- \rightarrow Co(0)$ with $E_p \approx -1.0$ V in a neutral medium¹³. Differential pulse polarogram of As is known to show three current peaks at potentials $\approx -0.4, -0.6$ and -0.8 V in a pronounced acidic medium¹⁰. Reduction of $As^{III} \rightarrow As^0$ ($E_p \approx -0.4$ V) accounts for the first and is the reference peak in the present determination. The second is a typical maxima and the third is accounted for further reduction of $As^0 \rightarrow As^{III}$. The maxima probably originates due to evolution of hydrogen catalysed by non-dissociated arsenous acid molecules¹⁰.

A wide variety of substances have been studied as supporting electrolytes in As^{III} and Co^{II} determinations¹¹⁻¹⁴. Of the various electrolytes studied in the present work (Table 1) 1.25 M HCl and 0.05 M KNO₃ were found to be more suitable for arsenic and cobalt, respectively. The choice was based on obtainment of higher 'ip' value, better base line and symmetry of pulsed steps.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF SUPPORTING ELECTROLYTE
As^{III}=5 ppm, Co^{II}=5 ppm

Sl. no.	As ^{III} Supporting electrolyte (M)	E _p V	Co ^{II} Supporting electrolyte (M)	E _p V
1.	H ₂ SO ₄ (0.5)	-0.450	H ₂ SO ₄ (1.0)	—
2.	HNO ₃ (1.0)	-0.445	HNO ₃ (1.0)	—
3.	H ₃ PO ₄ (1.0)	—	HCl (1.0)	—
4.	HClO ₄ (1.0)	-0.460	KSCN (0.05)	-1.10
5.	CH ₃ COOH (1.0)	—	NH ₄ Cl-NH ₄ OH (0.05)	-1.12
6.	HCl (1.25)	-0.380	KCl (0.05)	-1.08
7.	—	—	KNO ₃ (0.05)	-1.18

The effect of presence of three different maxima suppressors on the reduction characteristics of As^{III} and Co^{II} was also studied. Gelatin, Triton-X-100 and bromophenol blue, each in the concentration range of 2.0×10^{-6} to $2.0 \times 10^{-3}\%$ were maxima suppressors studied (Tables 2 and 3). A gelatin concentration of $2.0 \times 10^{-4}\%$ was found to be most

suitable for Co^{II} while for As^{III} it was $2.0 \times 10^{-3}\%$. The base line obtained in presence of gelatin was flat and better than with other suppressors.

Nitrogen was passed through the sample solution for different intervals of time at the rate of 2 ml min⁻¹, so as to expel dissolved oxygen. Nitrogen passing time of 15 min and 30 min were found most suitable for Co^{II} and As^{III}, respectively.

Fig. 1. Effect of HCl and KNO₃ concentrations on As^{III} (5 ppm) and Co^{II} (5 ppm).

Thus, the most suitable determination conditions for Co^{II} were 0.05 M KNO₃ as supporting electrolyte, $2.0 \times 10^{-4}\%$ gelatin as maxima suppressor and 15 min of nitrogen passing. For As^{III} determination 1.25 M HCl, $2.0 \times 10^{-3}\%$ gelatin and 30 min of nitrogen passing was most suitable.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF MAXIMA SUPPRESSORS ON As^{III} REDUCTION

As ^{III} ion	Maxima suppressor	% Peak depression with respect to $2 \times 10^{-3}\%$ gelatin			
		Maxima suppressor concentration $\times 10^{-4}\%$			
		0.2	1.0	10	20
0.6 ppm	Triton-X-100	6.56	7.05	18.00	23.30
	B. P. B.	7.05	9.97	15.32	23.35
	Gelatin	7.54	2.67	1.45	0
6.0 ppm	Triton-X-100	14.20	9.12	16.40	32.40
	B. P. B.	0	15.30	24.10	31.02
	Gelatin	0.36	3.64	5.10	0

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF MAXIMA SUPPRESSORS ON Co^{II} REDUCTION

Co ^{II} ion	Maxima suppressor	% Peak depression with respect to $2 \times 10^{-4}\%$ gelatin		
		Maxima suppressor concentration, $\times 10^{-4}\%$		
		0.2	2.0	20.0
5 ppm	Triton-X-100	36.50	41.90	53.84
	B. P. B.	34.29	30.13	29.31
	Gelatin	37.90	0	44.29

Under these conditions Co^{II} reduction peak appeared with $E_p = -1.18$ V. The minimum detection limit observed for Co^{II} was 0.4 ppm with a relative mean deviation of $\pm 2.8\%$. $\text{As}^{\text{III}} \rightarrow \text{As}^{\text{0}}$ reduction peak was obtained at $E_p = -0.380$ V. The minimum detection limit of As^{III} was 0.1 ppm and relative mean deviation was $\pm 1.02\%$.

Two calibration curves each for Co^{II} and As^{III} were obtained. In case of As^{III} , range was from 0.1 to 1.0 ppm and 1 to 10 ppm; with cobalt those extended between 0.4 to 2.6 ppm and 3 to 20 ppm. They are linear over the entire range of concentrations.

Tolerance of other cations in the determination procedure was also studied. Of the two, arsenic determination procedure shows higher tolerance towards most of the ions studied as when compared to cobalt determination procedure. Pb^{II} interferes seriously with As^{II} , while Zn^{II} and Ni^{III} interfere similarly in Co^{II} determination. The presence of 50 fold excess of Hg^{II} , Co^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} are tolerated in As determination. Presence of 8 fold excess of Pb^{II} and Hg^{II} are tolerated in Co determination.

An added procedural advantage is the possibility of simultaneous determination under the set experimental conditions. Both Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} can be determined in presence of As^{III} as they have widely differing E_p values (-0.24 and -0.9 V for Cu and Ni, respectively) and give appreciable diffusion current. 2 to 30 ppm of Cu^{II} could be determined with an error of $\pm 1.8\%$, while Ni^{II} could be determined in the concentration range of 6 to 30 ppm with an error of $\pm 1.6\%$.

So as to enhance the applicability of the method developed for arsenic determination to various samples, its selective separation from other contaminants of sample matrix was undertaken. As^{III} was distilled as its trihalide (AsCl_3). Further, after the sample digestion step As will be in As^{V} form and needs to be reduced to As^{III} state for the purpose of determination. This is achieved by the use of hydrazine sulphate as reductant^{1,2}. To a standard solution containing 50 μg of As^{III} , 25 ml of 6N HCl, 5 ml HBr solution and 0.5 g hydrazine sulphate was added; this mixture was then distilled at a temperature of 98° for 30 min. The distillate was collected in ice-cold water and arsenic content was determined by the above developed procedure after suitable dilutions. A 96% recovery of As^{III} with a relative mean deviation of $\pm 2.1\%$ was observed.

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Titrimetric Determinations Using Bromohydantoin as a New Oxidimetric Titrant in Aqueous Medium

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AS part of our programme for the investigation of new redox titrants¹⁻⁷, we report on the use of the sodium salt of 1-bromo-5,5-dimethylhydantoin as a new oxidimetric titrant in aqueous medium. For convenience, it may be called 'Bromohydantoin'(BH). Two types of direct titrations, potentiometric and visual indicator, have been developed for the determination of some common but diverse type reductants using this oxidant. The results of these determinations are presented in this note.

Experimental

BH was prepared from dibromohydantoin, which in turn, was prepared by the bromination of 5,5-dimethylhydantoin as reported earlier^{8,9}. Dibromohydantoin (28.6 g) was added in small quantities with stirring to a solution of sodium hydroxide (6 g in 50 ml water). On cooling to 5°, crystals of BH were separated and were filtered and dried